

An Acylated Glucopyranoside from *Indigofera oblongifolia*

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Indigofera Linn. is a very large genus and belongs to family Leguminosae¹. It is found abundantly in West Rajasthan. This report describes the isolation of a new nitropropanoyl α -glucopyranoside from its roots and stem along with the known compounds D(+)-pinitol, β -sitosterol, β -sitosterol- β -D-glucoside, lousifieserone and triacantanol, a plant growth regulator².

The air-dried powdered roots and stem of *I. oblongifolia* (1.8 kg) were extracted with petroleum ether, benzene, ethyl acetate and ethanol successively in a soxhlet. The extracts were concentrated under reduced pressure and the residue of ethyl acetate was charged on a silica gel column. It was eluted with hexane and increasing percentage of ethyl acetate. The major compound eluted from silica gel column chromatography furnished a solid which was crystallised from MeOH, m.p. 139–41° (Found: C, 37.18; H, 4.21; N, 9.59. C₁₈H₂₄N₄O₁₈ calcd. for : C, 36.98; H, 4.28; N, 9.58%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 720, 1 542, 1 360, 1 196, 850 cm⁻¹. Its ¹H nmr spectra ((CD₃)₂CO) displayed triplets at δ 3.08 (*J* 6 Hz) and 4.80 (*J* 6 Hz) assigned to acyl and methylene protons of the nitropropionic acid substituents respectively. The integration of all the protons indicated that it is

tetrasubstituted glucose. It displayed a triplet at δ 5.40 which became doublet on D₂O exchange and is assigned to the anomeric proton indicating that C-1 is not esterified³. The small coupling constant of H-1 (*J* 4 Hz) was attributed to an equatorial proton and hence the sugar moiety is an α -glucopyranose. Substitution at C-6 was confirmed by the multiplet due to methylene protons at δ 4.25 and H-5 appeared at δ 4.30 (d t, *J* 10 and 4 Hz). A double doublet at δ 4.92 (*J* 10 and 4 Hz), triplets at 5.66 (*J* 10 Hz) and 5.20 (*J* 10 Hz) were assigned to H-2, H-3 and H-4 respectively⁴.

The identity of sugar moiety was confirmed by GC of the corresponding alditol acetate prepared after acid hydrolysis and sodium borohydride reduction. Thus on the basis of the results compound 1 has been identified as 2,3,4,6-tetra(3-nitropropanoyl)- α -D-glucopyranoside (1).

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